

Column Chromatographic Separation of Lead from Alloy and Environmental Samples using Poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6)

B S MOHITE*, J. M. PATIL and D. N. ZAMBARE

Environmental Analytical Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

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Adsorption studies of lead have been carried out using crown ethers¹, crown ether sorbents² and crown polymers³, but no systematic efforts have been made for the use of poly(dibenzo-18-crown-6) for the adsorption chromatographic separation of lead from associated elements. The present communication describes the systematic investigation on the adsorption and separation studies of lead from other elements using poly(DB-18-C-6) from hydrochloric acid medium.

Results and Discussion

Adsorption studies of lead were carried out on poly(DB-18-C-6) by varying the concentration of HCl (0.5–10.0 M). It was found that there was quantitative adsorption of lead from 0.5–3.5 M HCl. Further adsorption studies of lead were carried out from 3.5 M HCl.

After adsorption, lead was eluted with various eluting agents, amongst which the most efficient were 6.0–8.0 M HCl and 7.0–8.0 M HBr. With 4.5 M HBr there was 15% elution and with 6.0 M 88%. Other eluting agents such as acetic acid, sulphuric acid and perchloric acid were found to be inefficient. The elution profiles of lead with HCl and HBr are shown in Fig. 1.

Effect of varying concentration of lead : In order to ascertain quantitative adsorption of lead on 1 g of poly(DB-18-C-6) column, various adsorption studies were carried out from 3.5 M

Fig 1 Elution studies of lead(II) with HCl and HBr

HCl concentration by varying the concentration of lead (10–100 mg dm⁻³). The solution (10 ml) was passed through the column and there was quantitative adsorption of lead upto the con-

centration of 50 mg dm⁻³. The extent of adsorption decreased with increase in concentration of lead. The capacity of poly(DB-18-C-6) for lead was found to be 2.41 mmol g⁻¹ of crown polymer.

Separation of lead from binary mixtures : A binary mixture solution (3.5 M HCl) containing lead and foreign ion was passed through the column and subsequently the column was washed with 3.5 M HCl. Those foreign ions which were not adsorbed on poly(DB-18-C-6), passed through the column. Most of the foreign ions were not adsorbed (Table 1). K, Ba, Tl^{III} and Mo^{VI} were adsorbed quantitatively, whereas Rb was adsorbed to the extent of 80%. The adsorbed K, Rb and Ba were eluted by washing the column with water, while Mo^{VI} was eluted with 0.5 M ammonium hydroxide. Most of the anions were also tolerated in higher ratios.

Separation of lead from multicomponent mixtures : Lead was separated from various elements in multicomponent mixture. When a mixture containing M, K/Ba, Pb and Mo (where M = Cs⁺, Sr²⁺, La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Ga³⁺, Cr³⁺, V⁵⁺) was passed through the column at 3.5 M HCl concentration, M was not adsorbed and hence passed through the column, whereas other elements were adsorbed on the column. The adsorbed K/Ba was eluted with water. Lead was then eluted with 6 M HCl and finally Mo was eluted with 0.5 M ammonium hydroxide.

The important feature of this method is that it permits the separation of lead from a number of elements such as Mo, Ba, Ce, Cs, Th, Cr, V etc. The method was applied to the analysis of lead in various samples, such as alloy and environmental samples. The proposed method is very simple, rapid, selective and reproducible.

Experimental

A crown ether polymer [poly(DB-18-C-6)] (Merck) was used after screening to 100–200 mesh. Poly(DB-18-C-6) (0.8 g) was slurried with distilled deionised water, poured into a chromatographic column and used after being preconditioned with HCl.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF LEAD FROM BINARY MIXTURES
Pb, 50 µg; 3.5 M HCl (Absorption);

6 M HCl (elution) Ion	Added as	Tolerance limit mg
Li ⁺	LiCl	2.50
Na ⁺	NaCl	3.00
*K ⁺	KCl	2.00
*Rb ⁺	RbCl	5.00
Cs ⁺	CaCl	4.50
NH ₄ ⁺	NH ₄ Cl	6.00
Be ²⁺	Be(NO ₃) ₂ .4H ₂ O	5.00
Mg ²⁺	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	7.00
Ca ²⁺	CaCl ₂	6.00
Sr ²⁺	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	3.00
*Ba ²⁺	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	4.00
Co ²⁺	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	3.00
Ni ²⁺	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	5.00
Cu ²⁺	CuCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	1.20
Zn ²⁺	ZnCl ₂	3.50
Mn ²⁺	MnCl ₂ .4H ₂ O	2.50
Sn ²⁺	SnCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	2.50
Cr ³⁺	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	4.00
Fe ³⁺	FeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O	0.50
Al ³⁺	Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	2.50
La ³⁺	La(NO ₃) ₃ .6H ₂ O	7.00
Ce ³⁺	CeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O	5.00
Bi ³⁺	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ .5H ₂ O	1.00
Ga ³⁺	GaCl ₃	3.00
In ³⁺	InCl ₃ .4H ₂ O	3.00
*Tl ³⁺	Tl(NO ₃) ₃ .3H ₂ O	0.50
Sb ³⁺	SbCl ₃	3.50
Ge ⁴⁺	Na ₂ GeO ₃	2.50
Th ⁴⁺	Th(NO ₃) ₄	5.00
V ⁵⁺	NH ₄ VO ₃	3.50
U ⁶⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	5.00
*Mo ⁶⁺	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	2.00
W ⁶⁺	Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	1.50
Br ⁻	BHr	9.50
I ⁻	HI	8.00
NO ₃ ⁻	HNO ₃	8.50
SCN ⁻	NaSCN	6.50
ClO ₄ ⁻	HClO ₄	7.00
CH ₃ COO ⁻	CH ₃ COOH	10.00
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ C ₂ O ₄	6.00
PO ₄ ³⁻	H ₃ PO ₄	5.00
Ascorbate	Ascorbic acid	6.00
Tartrate	Tartaric acid	5.00
Citrate	Citric acid	6.50
EDTA	EDTA	7.00

*Adsorbed.

A stock solution of lead (5 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared and standardised complexometrically⁴. Diluted solutions containing $50 \text{ } \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of lead were prepared by appropriate dilution.

Procedure : An aliquot of solution containing $50 \text{ } \mu\text{g}$ of Pb was mixed with HCl in the concentration range $0.5\text{--}10 \text{ M}$ in a total volume of 10 ml . The solution was then passed through the column, preconditioned with HCl of the same acidity as that of the sample solution, at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min^{-1} . The column was washed subsequently with HCl of the same acidity. The adsorbed lead was then eluted with different eluting agents at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min^{-1} . Fractions (2 ml) were collected and after evaporating the acid, it was extracted with water and the lead content was determined spectrophotometrically with PAR at 530 nm ⁵. The concentration of lead was calculated from the calibration curve.

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